

Enhancement of retention time of *matra basti* by addition of *prakshep* of *shatavha* and *saindhav* in sesame oil in treating *dhatukshyatmaka janusandhigata vata*: A brief note

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Abstract

Acharya *Sushruta* mentioned maximum retention period of *snehika basti* is up to nine hours. If *snehika basti* retains for maximum time, then it's very effective. This is probably because there is enough time for absorption of the *Sneha*. Acharya *Sushruta* has stated that the action of *basti* is mainly due to its *virya* (specific action or property). He further elaborates that the drugs used in *basti* spread in the body from *pakwashaya* through appropriate channels; similarly as a tree gets irrigated at the root and nutrients circulate to all parts of the tree. *Basti* eliminates the morbid dosha from the entire body (i.e. from *rasa dhatu* to *shukra dhatu*) gradually and all dhatus get nourishment as per *Sushruta*. This is possible when *basti* retains inside for maximum duration. The management of osteoarthritis of knee is broadly divided into non-pharmacological, pharmacological, and surgical treatments. These treatments are either expensive or not available for common people in developing countries. *Basti* treatment is useful in such patients, especially in elderly persons having natural predominance of *vata dosha* in their body. As sesame oil [*tila taila*] possesses having specific properties like *snigdha*, *ushna*, *madhur*, *kashaya*, *tikta rasa* & is *ushna guna* in nature, hence it diminishes vitiated *vata* and removes *kapha*. Addition of powders of *shatavaha* and *sandhaiv* in sesame oil used for *basti*, helps the maximum retention of *matrabasti*, so its useful in managing *dhatkshyatmka janusandhigata vata*.

Keywords: Matrabasti; Prakshep; Jaunsandhigata Vata; Osteoarthritis of knee

1. Introduction

Basti karma is one of the procedures of *Panchakarma*. *Basti* [medicated enema] is a prime treatment for treating *vata* disorders. It is mainly of two types viz. *asthapana* and *anuvasana* ¹. *Matra Basti* is a type of *snehik basti*, the retention time of which can be enhanced by adding powders of *shatavha* and *saindhav*. The retention time of *matra basti* depends on many factors in patients. Instead of administration of *matra basti* by plain *tila taila*, it is observed that adding powder of fibrous herb *shatavha*, and *saindhav lavan* can enhance the efficacy of *matra basti*. *Shatavha* [fennel seeds] is also *tridosha* balancing. *Saindhav* [rock salt] removes *vibandha* and *stanbha* and also helps in alleviating *vata*. *Lavan rasa* is known for removing *stambha*, *sanghata*, *bandha*, *vidhmapana* and increases *agni*.

Osteoarthritis of knee is more prevalent in Indian population. This disease simulates to the *Sandhigata Vata*. It is one of the degenerative joint diseases, characterised by breakdown of joint cartilage, leading to pain, air filled bag like swelling and stiffness at the joints. Osteoarthritis is the 2nd most common disease in the world population i.e., 30%. Knee joint is the most affected site. The major risk factors associated with knee joint are old age, obesity, occupational knee bending etc. which makes it an important cause of disability. *Sandhigata Vata* is developed by the excessive intake of *vata* aggravating foods like pungent, bitter, astringent tasing food and due to excess exercise and exertion. ². Osteoarthritis

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is a degenerative joint disease due to the degradation of the joints, the articular cartilages and subchondral bone. It is caused by the mechanical stress to the joints and produces the symptoms like joint pain, swelling, stiffness etc. Even though the disease affects any joint in the body, most commonly involved joints are major joints and weight bearing joints of the body like hip and knee joint.

Matra basti is performed with *prakshepdravya*³ to normalize deranged *vata* in digestive tract. It promotes strength and restore general well-being. Tila taila is *ushna, tikshna, sukshma, vyavayi, sarak, vikasi, vrushya, srotovishodhak*, stability inducing, tonic, constructive, guru and preenam⁴. Its action alleviates *vata* and *kapha* and vitiates *pitta*. It relieves aching pain from joints and body.

There is no clear-cut definition of *sandhigata vāta*, but however the classical text of Āyurveda, *Charaka Samhitā* reveals that aggravated *vāta* enters in the joints and get established thereby producing swelling of the joints, which is felt like a bag filled with air and the pain occurs mainly during the flexion and extension of the joints.

The characteristics signs and symptoms with which the disease can be easily diagnosed are known as *rūpa*. While describing the *rūpa* it is explained⁵.

2. Mode of action of basti

It is the best effective treatment indicated in various conditions, especially in *Vāta Doṣa* predominant disorders. The *basti dravya* gets rid of mala and *vata* from the *pakvashaya* and has exerts alleviating effect in the sites *viza nabhi, kati, parshava, kukshi* [lover abdomen and pelvis]⁶.

Basti is an *ardha cikitsā* & is a treatment of choice on *vāta doṣa*. *Basti karma* is a unique and broad-spectrum therapeutic and preventive approach. Basti is the medicated enema using Ayurvedic oils, decoctions, herbs etc which was administered using bladder of goat in ancient time. The word 'Basti' is used here with meaning "to reside" or "to retain"⁷. The Ayurvedic oils are administered by anal route in the rectum. It has action in *sarvanga vata roga*.

Basti is described as an internal route of drug administration by Dalhana⁸ and is considered as one of the methods of *snehan*⁹. The prime site of *vata dosha* is mainly *pakvashaya*; and *basti* administered at this site can prevent aggravation of *vata* all over the body¹⁰. The type *apana vata* resides mainly in this region. *matra basti* is generally administered with only tila taila. However maximum retention of *matrabasti* with *Til Tail* mixed with *praksep dravya shatavaha* [Fennel seeds, *Foeniculum vulgare*] and *sandhaiv* [rock salt] can be more effective than use of *tila taila* alone. Recent research has suggested that rectal absorption can prove the good alternative route of drug administration as it provides partial avoidance of first portal pass metabolism.

3. Conclusion

As per our preliminary data, as *matra basti* (sesame oil) with *praksep dravya* has more retention time and may prove to be more effective. *Matra basti* (sesame oil) with *praksep dravya (shatavaha and sanidhav)* may help to prevent and cure the *dhatukshyatmka janusandhigat vata*. *matra basti* with *praksep dravya* can definitely be used for *asthivaha srotas vyadhi* i.e. *dhatukshyatmka janusandhigat vata*.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

Authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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